

and green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* were given 1-2 d access feeding on diseased plants collected at Cianjur. The test insects were transferred to healthy Cisadane seedlings for 1-d inoculation feeding immediately after acquisition feeding and after a 9-d incubation. Only BPH that had 9-d incubation transmitted the disease (see table). Transmission by BPH also was confirmed using artificially inoculated source plants,

Seedlings inoculated at 7 d developed stunting and pale-green to pale-yellow discoloration 6-14 d after inoculation. Later symptoms consisted of striping or mottling on the second and third leaves from the youngest, rusty spots on lower leaves, and narrowing and shortening of leaf blades. Drying started from the tips of leaves before chlorosis spread over a whole leaf. Additional N failed to retrieve infected plants.

Most infected plants died 19-75 d after inoculation. Tiller numbers in

Transmission of a virulent strain of GSV by BPH and GLH.^a

Source plant	Insect	Inoculation		Plants inoculated (no.)	Plants infected (%)
		Insects/seedlings	Incubation period (d) after feeding on source		
Field collected	GLH (2d instar)	30/10	0	30	0
	BPH (2d instar)	30/10	0	30	0
	BPH (2d instar)	1/1	9	60	23.3
Greenhouse infected	BPH (2d instar)	30/10	9	40	7.5
Greenhouse infected	GLH (adult)	1/1	0	30	0
	GLH (adult)	1/1	9	30	0
	BPH (2d insty ^b)	10/1	9	9	22.2

^aInsects were allowed an acquisition access feeding of 1 or 2 d and then were given a 1-d inoculation access to 7-d-old seedlings after no or 9-d incubation period. ^bSeedlings inoculated at 30 d.

diseased plants were not significantly different from check until 30 d after inoculation. Plants that did not die produced numerous small tillers. Leaves with symptoms responded positively, but not consistently, to iodine.

Seedlings inoculated at 30 d exhibited uniform RTV-like orange-yellow discoloration on the third leaves at early

stages of infection. Neither stunting nor narrowing of leaves was conspicuous in 20 d after inoculation. However, later symptoms were not markedly different from those in 7-d-old seedlings.

These results show that the infectious agent is a virulent strain of GSV. A recent field survey found the strain occurring widely in Central Java. □

Insect management

Influence of carbofuran dose and time of application on control of rice water weevil (RWW)

R. Meneses-Carbonell, Rice Experiment Station "Sur del Jibaro", Sancti-Spiritus, Cuba

The RWW *Lissorhoptrus brevisrostris* affects 10-28% of the land planted to rice in Cuba, and it is the most difficult insect pest to control.

Different levels of carbofuran 5% G (0.6-1.9 kg ai/ha) were broadcast before sowing (test 1) and 25 d after germination (DAG) (test 2).

Three plants of variety J-104 were sown in 12-cm-diameter clay pots. In test 1, they were inoculated with 20 RWW adults/pot 20 DAG. In test 2, 20 first-instar larvae/pot were inoculated the day after insecticide application.

All levels of carbofuran controlled RWW adults and larvae. Control was

Effect of different levels of carbofuran 5% G on RWW.^a Sancti-Spiritus, Cuba.

Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Adult mortality (%)		Larvae mortality (%) 10 DAI
	2 DAI	14 DAI	
0.6	72	82	98
0.8	70	88	98
0.9	68	84	98
1.1	68	86	96
1.5	70	88	100
1.9	74	88	100
Check	2	2	0

^aAv of 4 replications. DAI = days after inoculation.

greater when carbofuran was applied 25 DAG than when it was broadcast before sowing (see table).

In the field, the insect shows similar behavior in respect to the time of invasion.

Application must be done when larvae are leaving the leaf sheath after hatching; that is the stage most susceptible to insecticides. □

Effect of neem seed bitters (NSB) on green leafhopper (GLH) survival and rice tungro virus (RTV) transmission

R. C. Saxena and M. E. M. Boncodin, Entomology Department, IRRI

A reduction in phloem feeding by GLH *Nephotettix virescens*, the vector of RTV disease, is observed in plants with foliar or systemic application of NSB. RTV is phloem-specific. We evaluated RTV transmission efficiency of GLH feeding on NSB-treated plants.

Two-week-old TN1 seedlings were treated by 24-h root immersion or sprayed with 2,500 ppm NSB. Untreated seedlings were used as check. Each seedling was placed in a 15- × 1.5-cm test tube covered with nylon mesh and arranged by treatment.

Newly emerged GLH females reared on virus-free TN1 plants were allowed a 3-d acquisition feeding on source plants. One viruliferous GLH was transferred to each tube. One day after infestation

(DAI), surviving insects were transferred to freshly treated seedlings. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in seedboxes for disease development. Successive inoculation feeding continued up to 5 d. RTV symptoms were observed at 20 DAI.

GLH survival decreased significantly after 2-d exposure to systemically treated plants. Although survival of GLH exposed to foliar NSB-treated seedlings was not significantly different from check, ability to transmit RTV was significantly lower than that of untreated seedlings (see table).

Survival of GLH females and RTV transmission after 5 d exposure to TN1 rice seedlings treated with 2,500 ppm NSB.^a IRRI, 1987.

Treatment	GLH survival (%)				RTV infection (%)	
	1d	2d	3d	5d	1d	2d
Foliar	95 a	91 b	84 b	69 b	38 b	8 a
Systemic	90 a	74 a	69 a	51 a	17 a	4 a
Check	95 a	89 b	84 b	74 b	65 c	22 a

^aAv of 5 replications, 30 GLH and 30 TN1 seedlings/replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Systemic NSB application was best against RTV transmission. RTV transmission efficiency of the vector

became negligible after 2d inoculation feeding in check as well as in treated plants. □

Compatible insecticides and fungicides to control leafhopper (LF) and sheath rot (ShR) in rice

N. Raju, R. Saroja, and M. Suriachandrasekhar, Rice Research Station, Tirur 602025, India

We studied the compatibility of commonly used insecticides phosphamidon, monocrotophos, and chlorpyrifos with popular fungicides edifenphos, mancozeb, and carbendazim

during 1985-86 and 1986-87. Field trials consisted of 10 treatments replicated 3 times. In both years, 25-d-old Co 43 seedlings were planted in 10-m² plots at 20- × 10-cm spacing. Combined sprays were applied at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting.

Only rice LF and ShR occurred during the study. In both years, combined spraying of monocrotophos with any one of the three fungicides was the most effective treatment, keeping LF infestation well below economic injury level (<5%). In 1986-87, combined

spraying of monocrotophos with carbendazim resulted in the lowest incidence of ShR (see table).

In both years, combined spraying of monocrotophos with the three fungicides resulted in the highest yields. □

Efficacy and compatibility of insecticides and fungicides in the control of rice pests and diseases. Rice Research Station, Tirur, India, 1985-86 and 1986-87.

Treatment	1985-86		1986-87		
	LF-damaged leaves (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)	LF-damaged leaves (%)	ShR infected tillers (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Phosphamidon 250 ml/ha + edifenphos 500 ml/ha	29	3.1	15	7.0	4.2
Phosphamidon 250 ml/ha + mancozeb 1000 g/ha	19	3.0	14	6.6	4.1
Phosphamidon 250 ml/ha + carbendazim 250 g/ha	32	2.8	16	8.2	3.8
Monocrotophos 500 ml/ha + edifenphos 500 ml/ha	4	3.4	2	6.0	4.5
Monocrotophos 500 ml/ha + mancozeb 1000 g/ha	3	3.6	3	6.0	4.2
Monocrotophos 500 ml/ha + carbendazim 250 g/ha	3	3.2	2	4.9	4.2
Chlorpyrifos 500 ml/ha + edifenphos 500 ml/ha	11	3.1	7	7.0	4.2
Chlorpyrifos 500 ml/ha + mancozeb 1000 g/ha	15	2.8	9	6.2	3.9
Chlorpyrifos 500 ml/ha + carbendazim 250 g/ha	17	2.9	25	5.6	4.0
Control	63	2.7	77	13.5	3.1
CD (P=0.05)	5.0	1.5	15.4	5.5	0.4

Brown planthopper (BPH) outbreak in Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu

K. Natarajan, M.S. Venugopal, and S. Chelliah, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

During the Jun-Sep 1987 drought due to failure of the monsoon, a BPH outbreak in Sivapurani, Kondasamudram, and Kurichi villages of Kumbakonam division, Thanjavur District, caused typical hopperburn symptoms on IR50. Approximately 100 ha were affected. Farmers applied double the recommended N as basal fertilizer. Because the insecticides used were not directed toward the base of the plants, control was inadequate. Furthermore, the farmers sprayed quinalphos, a resurgence causing insecticide, which aggravated the pest population.

Unsprayed fields recorded 56 hoppers/hill; phosphamidon-sprayed fields had 8 hoppers/hill. Where quinalphos was sprayed, populations